

Tribo-mechanical behavior of spark plasma sintered multiwalled carbon nanotube reinforced AlN rich SiAlON polytype composites

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Abstract

Effect of MWCNT reinforcement on tribomechanical properties of SPS processed (2000°C/10 min/40 MPa) additive free, dense SiAlON polytype has been investigated. FESEM observation confirmed successful retention of CNT's tubular morphology with limited crumbling/shortening of defective CNTs after SPS processing. Besides formation of equiaxed and fibre-like SiAlON grains, different CNT/SiAlON interactions were also observed in the composite. Depending on test load, the 0.5 wt.% CNT/SiAlON composite offered 7.5–25% and 10–16% higher HV and K_{IC} values, respectively, over the monolith. Both sintered compositions showed positive *indentation size effect* and rising *R-curve* behaviour within the investigated loading range. More than 30% improvement in wear resistance was obtained for the composite compared to the pure polytype when scratched against a sharp diamond indenter under dry condition. Changes in tribomechanical properties of pure polytype through MWCNT reinforcement have been discussed with the help of microstructural and wear track features.

Key words: SiAlON polytype; MWCNT, SPS, Tribo-mechanical properties